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A first glance at the UK Biobank Database

Gene SLC25A15 in patients with self-reported Chronic Fatigue Syndrome

Paolo Maccallini

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1 UK Biobank study

The UK Biobank is a large-scale biomedical database that includes genetic data on 500,000 UK citizens ([Sudlow, C et al. 2015](#)). Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/CFS) is among the phenotypes reported by participants. The total number of ME/CFS patients included is 1208 females and 451 males, with control groups of more than 150 k individuals each. For each individual 805,426 variants (both SNPs and short InDels) were genotyped. From them, up to 30 million variant can be imputed using haplotype maps. This is the biggest GWAS study on ME/CFS patients ever made, so far. Many research groups have analyzed this huge quantity of data and one of the most promising results, according to ([Dibble J. et al. 2020](#)) is the one described in what follows.

Label	Explanation of labels (download)	Variant details (download)
variant	Variant identifier in the form "chr:pos:ref:alt", where "ref" is aligned to the forward strand of GRCh37 and "alt" is the effect allele (use this to join with variant annotation file)	13:41353297:G:A
rsid	rsid (not guaranteed to be unique)	rs7337312
varid	Unique variant identifier included in imputed BGEN files	rs7337312
ref	Reference allele on the forward strand	G
alt	Alternate allele (not necessarily minor allele)	A
consequence	Consequence annotated using VEP version 85	regulatory_region_variant
consequence_category	Category of VEP-annotated consequence ("ptv", "missense", "synonymous", "non_coding")	non_coding
AC	Alternate ¹ allele count (calculated using hardcall genotypes ²)	365235
AF ³	Alternate allele frequency (calculated using hardcall genotypes)	0.505594
minor_allele	Minor allele (equal to ref allele when AF > 0.5, otherwise equal to alt allele)	G
minor_AF	Minor allele frequency (calculated using hardcall genotypes)	0.494406
n_called	Number of samples with defined genotype at this variant	361194
n_not_called	Number of samples without a defined genotype at this variant	0

Table 1. In the third column some of the details for the variant we are interested in, from the variants.tsv file. The column on the center collects the explanations of the labels, from the README file.

1.1 Gene SLC25A15 (Neale's Lab)

The collection of the analysis generated by Neale's Lab with the UK Biobank data is available [here](#). In line 2 of that file, you can download an explanation of the labels (README). At lines 9 and 10 you

¹ The fact that AC and AF both refer to the alternate allele is indicated in the FAQ page of Neale Lab ([here](#)).

² Hardcall genotype values means: 0/1/2 for homRef/het/homVar ([Ref](#)).

³ When AF>0.5 then the alternative allele is the major allele, while the reference allele is the minor allele (see also Table 2).

can download a collection of the phenotypes and of some of the attributes of the relative sample, for females and males respectively (phenotypes.female.tsv, phenotypes.male.tsv). We are interested in phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). In line 11 you find a file that contains the details on each variant (variants.tsv). You must unzip the files before opening them with Excel. To better read the file for chromosome 13, ask to open it from line 10,000,000 or so, otherwise it will open only the call for the first two chromosomes (at least this is what happens with my machine). You must set the dot as the separator for decimal digits! I have collected in Table 1 the data from variants.tsv for the variant we are interested in. In the central column, you find also the explanation of the labels from the README file.

CASES	Alternative allele frequency	Major allele frequency	Minor allele frequency	
AF>0.5	AF	AF	minor_AF = 1.0 - AF	alternative allele = major allele reference allele = minor allele
AF<0.5	AF	-	AF	alternative allele = minor allele reference allele = major allele

Table 2. AF is the alternative allele frequency. When AF>0, it is also the frequency of the major allele and in this case minor_AF = 1.0 - AF. In the present case when have that A is the alternative allele and since AF=0.505594, then it is also the major allele, while G is the minor one and minor_AF = 1.0 - AF = 0,494406.

Note that AF is the alternative allele frequency. When AF>0, it is also the frequency of the major allele and in this case minor_AF = 1.0 - AF (Table 2). In the present case we have that A is the alternative allele and since AF=0.505594, then it is also the major allele, while G is the minor one and minor_AF = 1.0 - AF = 0,494406.

Lable	Explanation of labels (download)	F (download)	M (download)
phenotype	Unique phenotype identifier. Format differs depending on the source of the phenotype	20002_1482	
n_cases	For case/control phenotypes, number of case samples within the analysis subset	1208	451
n_controls	For case/control phenotypes, number of control samples within the analysis subset	192945	166537
minor_AF	Frequency of the minor allele in the n_complete_samples defined for this phenotype	0.494672	0.494077
expected_case_minor_AC	(Optional) For case/control phenotypes, calculated as (2 * minor_AF * n_cases)	1195.13	445.658
n_complete_samples	Number of samples defined for this phenotype	194153	166988
AC	Allele count of alternative allele ⁴ calculated on dosages within n_complete_samples	196222	168966
ytx	Dot product of phenotype vector y and genotype vector x (alt allele count in cases for case/control phenotypes)	1082	459
pval	p-value of beta significance test	2.55504 · 10 ⁻⁸	0.774073

Table 3. Genetic data for female patients and male patients, respectively, for the phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-

⁴ The alternative allele is the one defined as alternative in the variants.tsv file (Table 1). Allele A, in our case.

reported: chronic fatigue syndrome) for the variant we are interested in.

At lines 1369 and 1370 (files 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.female.tsv and 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.male.tsv, respectively) you find the genetic data for female patients and male patients, respectively, for the phenotype 20002_1482 (Non-cancer illness code, self-reported: chronic fatigue syndrome). I have collected in Table 3 the details from these two files for the variant we are interested in.

Groups		N.	Allele A (Alt, Major)		Allele G (Ref, Minor)		pval
			count	frequency	count	frequency	
F	Cases	1208	1082	1082: (2x1208) = 0.447848	(2x1208) – 1082 = 1334	1334: (2x1208) = 0.552152	2.55 · 10⁻⁸
	Controls	192945	196222 – 1082 = 195140	195140: (2x192945) = 0.505688	(2x192945) – 195140 = 190750	190750: (2x192945) = 0.494312	
	Cases + Controls	194153	196222	196222: (2x194153) = 0.505328	0.494672x2 x194153 = 192084	0.494672	
M	Cases	451	459	459: (2x451) = 0.508869	(2x451) – 459 = 443	443: (2x451) = 0.491131	0.774073
	Controls	166537	168966 – 459 = 168507	168507: (2x166537) = 0.505915	(2x166537) – 168507 = 164567	164567: (2x166537) = 0.494085	
	Cases + Controls	166988	168966	168966: (2x166988) = 0.505922	0.494077x2 x166988 = 165010	0.494077	
Total UK Biobank Sample		361194	365235	0.505594	(2x361194) – 365235 = 357153	0.494406	
General population (global gnomAD)			-	0.54052	-	0.45948	

Table 4. Summary of the salient details for the variant we are interested in, from Table 1 and Table 3. Numbers in black are directly collected from the aforementioned tables. Numbers in red have been calculated from those in black.

I have then collected in Table 4 a subset of relevant details from both Table 1 and Table 3 (numbers in black). Numbers in red are derived from the ones in black as described in the relative cells. Values in red are evaluated by the code that follows, as well.

1.1.1 Statistics

In genome-wide associations studies (GWAS) like the one we are writing about here, the number of SNPs taken into account is from 0.5 million up to 2.5 million. In this case, testing for multiple comparisons implies a cut off for the p value of 5×10^{-8} , when we are considering SNPs with a minor allele frequency above 5% (like the case of the SNP we are here discussing) ([Fadista J et al. 2016](#)). Files from Neale’s Lab contain their statistical tests for significance (label pval in Table 3, Table 4).

But another way to test for significance, to my understanding, is by calculating the probability of the distribution of alleles we see in patients if we assume for one of the two alleles (the minor one, for instance) the frequency it has in the whole sample. Let's now consider data collected in Table 5, where $f_D(A)$ is the frequency of allele A among patients, while $f_H(A)$ is the frequency of the same allele among healthy subjects; $AC_D(A)$ is the allele count for A among patients, $AC_H(A)$ is the count of the same allele among controls, etc. The probability that we have an allele count $k \leq f_D(A)2n_D = AC_D(A)$ among patients, if the frequency is the one we find in controls, is

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad P(k \leq AC_D(A)) = \sum_{k=1}^{AC_D(A)} p(k) = \sum_{k=1}^{AC_D(A)} \binom{2n_D}{k} f_H(A)^k (1 - f_H(A))^{2n_D - k}$$

which is equal to $7.15045 \cdot 10^{-9}$. The probability of having an allele count $k \geq 2n_D(f_H(A) + |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|)$ is given by

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad P(k \geq 2n_D(f_H(A) + |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|)) = \sum_{k=2n_D(f_H(A) + |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|)}^{2n_D} p(k) = 7.80208 \cdot 10^{-9}$$

	Disease ($n_D = 1208$)	Healthy ($n_H = 192945$)
$f(A)$	$f_D(A) = 0.447848$	$f_H(A) = 0.505688$
$f(a)$	$f_D(a) = 1 - f_D(A)$	$f_H(a) = 1 - f_H(A)$
$AC(A)$	$AC_D(A) = 1082$	$AC_H(A) = 195140$
$AC(a)$	$AC_D(a) = 2n_D - AC_D(A)$	$AC_H(a) = 2n_H - AC_H(A)$

Table 5. Allele frequencies for the comparison female patients vs female controls for variant rs7337312.

Then, we can conclude that the probability we are searching for is

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \begin{cases} P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = \sum_{k=1}^{AC_D(A)} p(k) + \sum_{k=2n_D(f_H(A) + |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|)}^{2n_D} p(k) \\ p(k) = \binom{2n_D}{k} f_H(A)^k (1 - f_H(A))^{2n_D - k} \end{cases}$$

In our case we have $P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$. We can also use the normal approximation by assuming for the patient group the frequency of the healthy subjects $f_H(A)$: we have the binomial law $B(2n_D, f_H(A))$ which is approximated by the normal law $N(\sigma^2 = 2n_D f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A)), \mu = 2n_D f_H(A))$. By using this distribution

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad P(k \leq AC_D(A)) = \Phi\left(\frac{2n_D f_D(A) - 2n_D f_H(A)}{\sqrt{2n_D f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right) = 6.48854 \cdot 10^{-9}$$

Then we have

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = 2\Phi\left(\sqrt{\frac{2n_D(f_D(A) - f_H(A))^2}{f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right)$$

In our case we have $P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = 1.298 \cdot 10^{-8}$.

1.1.1.1 Script

This script calculates the probability in Eq. 5 by using Octave's function `normcdf(x, m, s)` which evaluates $\Phi\left(\frac{x-m}{s}\right)$. Note now that in general Eq. 4 assumes the following form:

$$P(k \leq AC_D(A)) = \begin{cases} \Phi\left(\frac{2n_D f_D(A) - 2n_D f_H(A)}{\sqrt{2n_D f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) \leq f_H(A) \\ 1 - \Phi\left(\frac{2n_D f_D(A) - 2n_D f_H(A)}{\sqrt{f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) > f_H(A) \end{cases}$$

Hence, Eq. 5 must be written

$$P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = \begin{cases} 2\Phi\left(\frac{2n_D f_D(A) - 2n_D f_H(A)}{\sqrt{f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) \leq f_H(A) \\ 2 - 2\Phi\left(\frac{2n_D f_D(A) - 2n_D f_H(A)}{\sqrt{f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) > f_H(A) \end{cases}$$

Or, in other words

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad P(|f(A) - f_D(A)| \geq |f_H(A) - f_D(A)|) = \begin{cases} 2\Phi\left(\frac{x-m}{s}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) \leq f_H(A) \\ 2 - 2\Phi\left(\frac{x-m}{s}\right) & \leftarrow f_D(A) > f_H(A) \end{cases}$$

with $x = 2n_D f_D(A)$, $m = 2n_D f_H(A)$, $s = \sqrt{f_H(A)(1 - f_H(A))}$.

```
% file name = test
% date of creation = 26/02/2022
clear all
pkg load statistics
%-----
% parameters
%-----
```

```

fD = 0.447848
fH = 0.505688
nD = 1208
nH = 192945
%-----
% p value
%-----
x = 2*nD*fD;
m = 2*nD*fH;
s = sqrt( 2*nD*fH*(1-fH) );
if (fD <= fH)
    p = double(2*normcdf(x,m,s))
else
    p = double(2 - 2*normcdf(x,m,s))
endif
%-----

```

1.1.1.2 Notes on the binomial distribution

Now, we have a problem here: a double-precision floating-point variable has usually a range included between 10^{-308} and 10^{308} , which means that $170!$ is the largest factorial we can store in it. You can find a detailed discussion of these topics in ([Maccallini P. 2017](#)). Now, how can we avoid storing a number greater than the capacity of the variable available for it? One possible solution is to use Stirling's approximation for the binomial coefficient:

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad \binom{n}{k} \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi k}} \left(\frac{n}{k}\right)^k \left(\frac{n}{n-k}\right)^{\left(n-k+\frac{1}{2}\right)}, \quad \forall n \neq k$$

Another step then is to calculate the logarithm (of base 10, for instance) of the binomial coefficient, using the above approximation. We have:

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad \log_{10} \binom{n}{k} \sim \log_{10} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi k}} + k \log_{10} \left(\frac{n}{k}\right) + \left(n - k + \frac{1}{2}\right) \log_{10} \left(\frac{n}{n-k}\right), \quad \forall n \neq k$$

Then, the binomial distribution becomes:

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad \log_{10} p(k) \sim \log_{10} p^k + \log_{10} (1-p)^{2m-k} + \log_{10} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi k}} + k \log_{10} \left(\frac{n}{k}\right) + \left(n - k + \frac{1}{2}\right) \log_{10} \left(\frac{n}{n-k}\right)$$

The other solution is to write the binomial coefficient as follows:

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} = \frac{n(n-1) \dots (n-k+1)(n-k)!}{k!(n-k)!} = \frac{n(n-1) \dots (n-k+1)}{k!} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad \binom{n}{k} = \frac{n}{k} \cdot \frac{n-1}{k-1} \cdot \frac{n-2}{k-2} \cdots \frac{n-k+1}{k-k+1}$$

As you can see, if we calculate separately each of the multiplicative ratios, we deal with much smaller numbers. To achieve that, you might need to write a couple of lines of code, like the following ones, written in Octave.

```
C_B=1;
```

```

for i=1:l:k
  C_B=C_B*(n-i+1)/(k-i+1);
end

```


Figure 1. Gene expression of ornithine transporter I in several tissues, for the gene carrying the base A at position 41353297 of chromosome 13 (taken from GTExPORTAL, [here](#)).

Also in this case it might be necessary to use the trick of logarithms to deal with smaller numbers:

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \log_{10} p(k) = \log_{10} p^k + \log_{10} (1-p)^{2m-k} + \sum_1^k \log_{10} \frac{n-k+1}{k-k+1}$$

and the code becomes the following one

```
L_C_B=0.;
for i=1:1:k
    L_C_B = L_C_B + log10( (n-i+1)/(k-i+1) );
end
```


Figure 2. Urea cycle in an hepatocyte. From (Salway J. G. 2017), with changes. Chart by Paolo Maccallini.

1.1.2 Possible meaning of this result

Gene [SLC25A15](#) encodes mitochondrial ornithine transporter I. Variant 13:41353297:G:A (rs7337312) is not included in the exons of the genes. In other words, this part of the gene is not

translated into the actual transporter. It is believed to have a regulatory role on the expression of the gene, though (Table 1). More precisely, base A leads to a slightly higher expression of the transporter in several tissues, as you can see in Figure 1 (taken from GTExPORTAL, [here](#)). So, for instance, the expression of the transporter in the esophagus when the base A is present instead of base G, has a NES (normalized enrichment score) of 0.377 which means that if the expression of the transporter is X when the base G is present, then it will be $X + 0.377X$ when the base A is present, and so forth. Thus, we can say that female patients with ME/CFS tend to have a lower than normal expression of this transporter in several tissues (including various regions of the brain, like the hippocampus, amygdala, caudate, anterior cingulate cortex, putamen, and substantia nigra; Figure 1).

Transporter (gene)	Metabolite	Enzyme (gene)	
	ammonium	carbamoyl phosphate synthetase I (CPS1)	ornithine transcarbamoylase (OTC)
	carbamoyl phosphate		
ornithine translocase (SLC25A15)	ornithine	argininosuccinate synthase I (ASS1)	argininosuccinate lyase (ASL)
	citrulline		
	aspartate	arginase 1 (ARG1)	
	argininosuccinate		
	fumarate		
	arginine		
ornithine translocase (SLC25A15)	ornithine		
	urea		

Table 6. Enzymes and metabolites involved in the Urea Cycle.

What might be the consequence of this slight reduction in expression of this transporter is not clear: when the gene is not functioning at all we see an increase in plasma ammonia (episodically or postprandially) and a chronic increase in plasma ornithine ([R](#)). These abnormalities are because ornithine translocase is involved in the transport of ornithine inside mitochondria, where it is metabolized into citrulline and in doing so it consumes ammonium (NH_4^+), the conjugate acid of ammonia (NH_3) (see Figure 2, Table 6).

1.1.3 Metabolites of the urea cycle in the blood of ME/CFS patients

I have looked at studies that have measured the metabolites of the urea cycle among ME/CFS patients (Table 7, Figure 3). While a study reported an increase in ornithine and a decrease in citrulline and urea (all abnormalities compatible with reduced transport of ornithine inside mitochondria) ([Yamano E. et al. 2016](#)), this result was not confirmed by other studies. It might be noted though that a tendency towards a reduction in urea among female patients (but not in males) has been reported in ([Naviaux R.K. et al. 2016](#)) (Figure 3) but it doesn't reach statistical significance. In a 2015 paper, serum amino acids were measured in both male ME/CFS patients and in female ones and the result was that serum level of several amino acids was reduced in females, but not in males ([Fluge Ø. et al. 2015](#)), as reported in Table 7. One might speculate that this result reflects higher catabolism of amino acids in females than in males with ME/CFS and that this would have more negative consequences in women with one or two copies of SLC25A15 with base G than in those with base A at position 41353297 of chromosome 13. If that was the case, the mutation would be a predisposition to a higher burden of symptoms in females, rather than a predisposition to the disease itself. I have to think more deeply about that.

Pts	sample	criteria	ammonium / ammonia	ornithine	arginine	citrulline	urea	reference
19 F	plasma	CDC Oxford	NA	=	=	=	NA	(Jones M.G. et al. 2005) ⁵
11 M								
41 F	plasma	CDC	NA	↑	=	↓	↓	(Yamano E. et al. 2016) ⁶
6 M								
23 F	plasma	IOM CCC CDC	NA	=	↑	=	=	(Naviaux R.K. et al. 2016) ⁷
22 M			NA	=	↑	=	=	
34 F	serum	CCC	NA	=	=	=	NA	(Armstrong C. et al. 2017) ⁸
15 F	plasma	CDC	NA	=	NA	NA	NA	(Germain et al. 2017) ⁹
26 F	plasma	CDC	NA	=	=	=	NA	(Germain A. et al. 2020) ¹⁰

Table 7. Results of metabolomic studies that have looked at metabolites of the cycle of Urea in ME/CFS patients.

Figure 3. Metabolites of the urea cycle from Figure S.4 of Supporting Information of (Naviaux R.K. et al. 2016). Green stands for a Z score ≤ 2.00 and red indicates a Z score ≥ 2 . Z score is calculated as follows: $(\text{mean value in patients} - \text{mean value in controls}) / \text{standard deviation in controls}$. White indicates a Z score of zero.

⁵ From Table 3.

⁶ From Fig. 1

⁷ From paragraph “*Pyrroline-5-Carboxylate and Arginine Were Increased*” for arginine, citrulline, ornithine. Urea is included in the set of all the metabolites analysed (R) but it is present neither among the 61 most significant metabolites that differentiates male patients from controls nor in the analogous analysis for female patients (Table S1). It tends to be reduced in female patients and not in male patients, though, according to Figure S4, where green stands for a Z score ≤ 2.00 and red is a Z score ≥ 2 . Z score is calculated as follows: $(\text{mean value in patients} - \text{mean value in controls}) / \text{standard deviation in controls}$.

⁸ From a comparison between Fig. 1.b (blood metabolites with a statistically significant difference between patients and controls) and Fig. 2 (set of blood metabolites measured).

⁹ Ammonium, arginine, citrulline and urea are not present in the list of analysed metabolites available as supplementary material (R); ornithine is present in that file but it is not listed among metabolites with a statistically significant difference between patients and controls (Table 2).

¹⁰ Ornithine, citrulline, and arginine are present in the set of metabolites analysed (supplementary file 1, R) but not in those with a statistically significant difference between patients and controls (Table S1). Ammonium and urea are not present in the list of metabolites analysed.

cat.	amino acid	symbol	catabolism	results		
				M	F	
category I	alanine	Ala	⇒ pyruvate	↓	↓	
	cysteine	Cys		=	=	
	glycine	Gly		=	=	
	serine	Ser		=	↓	
	threonine	Thr		=	↓	
category II	isoleucine	Ile	⇒ Acetyl-CoA	=	↓	
	leucine	Leu		=	↓	
	lysine	Lys		=	↓	
	phenylalanine	Phe		=	↓	
	tryptophan	Trp		=	↓	
	tyrosine	Tyr		↓	↓	
	TOTAL			=	↓	
category III	methionine	Met	⇒ succinyl-CoA	=	↓	
	valine	Val		=	↓	
	histidine	His	⇒ α-ketoglutarate	=	↓	
	glutamine	Gln		Glx	=	↓
	glutamic acid	Glu			=	↓
	proline	Pro		=	↓	
	asparagine	Asn	Asx	⇒ fumarate ⇒ oxaloacetate	=	↓
	aspartate	Asp			=	↓
	TOTAL			=	↓	

Table 8. Amino acids in serum in patients with ME/CFS. From (Fluge Ø et al. 2015), with changes. Table by Paolo Maccallini.

1.1.4 Script

This is the script (Octave) I have written for analyzing data from the following files:

- variants.tsv
- 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.female.tsv and
- 20002_1482.gwas.imputed_v3.male.tsv

Its output is the same as the one in Table 4 and it also calculates statistical significance using the method described in par. 1.1.1. It can be used for any other variant (just changing the variables) in both cases $AF > 0.5$ and $AF < 0.5$, even though I have not tested it in the second case yet.

```

-----
% file name = biobank_neale_cfs_rs7337312
% date of creation = 4/10/2020
% chr:pos:ref:alt = 13:41353297:G:A
clear all
% data-----
% alleles
alt_al = 'A';           % alt allele
ref_al = 'G';           % ref allele
% whole sample
n_called = 361194;      % the whole UK biobank sample for this SNP
AF = 0.505594;          % alt allele frequency in n_called
% female cases-----
n_cases_f = 1208;       % number of female cases
ytx_f = 1082;           % alternative allele count in n_cases_f
% female controls
n_controls_f = 192945;  % number of female controls
% female cases + controls
n_complete_samples_f = 194153; % female cases + female controls
minor_AF_f = 0.494672; % frequency of the minor allele in n_complete_samples_f
AC_f = 196222;          % alternative allele count in n_complete_samples_f
% male cases-----
n_cases_m = 451;        % number of male cases
ytx_m = 459;            % alternative allele count in n_cases_m
% male controls-----
n_controls_m = 166537;  % number of male controls
% male cases + controls-----
n_complete_samples_m = 166988; % male cases + male controls
minor_AF_m = 0.494077; % frequency of the minor allele in n_complete_samples_m
AC_m = 168966;          % alternative allele count in n_complete_samples_m
% -----
% derived data
% -----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
    alt_string = strjoin ( {'The alt allele',alt_al,'is the major allele'}, ' ');
    minor_string = strjoin ( {'The ref allele',ref_al,'is the minor allele'}, ' ');
    minor_al = ref_al;
    major_al = alt_al;
else
    alt_string = strjoin ( {'The alt allele',alt_al,'is the minor allele'}, ' ');
    minor_string = strjoin ( {'The ref allele',ref_al,'is the major allele'}, ' ');
    minor_al = alt_al;
    major_al = ref_al;
endif
% female cases-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
    alt_AC_cases_f = ytx_f;
    major_AC_cases_f = alt_AC_cases_f;
    alt_AF_cases_f = alt_AC_cases_f/(2*n_cases_f);
    major_AF_cases_f = alt_AF_cases_f;
    minor_AC_cases_f = 2*n_cases_f - ytx_f;
    ref_AC_cases_f = minor_AC_cases_f;
    minor_AF_cases_f = minor_AC_cases_f/(2*n_cases_f);
    ref_AF_cases_f = minor_AF_cases_f;
else
    alt_AC_cases_f = ytx_f;
    minor_AC_cases_f = alt_AC_cases_f;
    alt_AF_cases_f = alt_AC_cases_f/(2*n_cases_f);
    minor_AF_cases_f = alt_AF_cases_f;

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ref_AC_case_f = 2*n_cases_f - ytx_f;
major_AC_case_f = ref_AC_case_f;
ref_AF_case_f = ref_AC_case_f/(2*n_cases_f);
major_AF_case_f = ref_AF_case_f;
endif
% female controls-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
alt_AC_controls_f = AC_f - alt_AC_cases_f;
major_AC_controls_f = alt_AC_controls_f;
alt_AF_controls_f = alt_AC_controls_f/(2*n_controls_f);
major_AF_controls_f = alt_AF_controls_f;
minor_AC_controls_f = (2*n_controls_f) - alt_AC_controls_f;
ref_AC_controls_f = minor_AC_controls_f;
minor_AF_controls_f = minor_AC_controls_f/(2*n_controls_f);
ref_AF_controls_f = minor_AF_controls_f;
else
alt_AC_controls_f = AC_f - alt_AC_cases_f;
minor_AC_controls_f = alt_AC_controls_f;
alt_AF_controls_f = alt_AC_controls_f/(2*n_controls_f);
minor_AF_controls_f = alt_AF_controls_f;
major_AC_controls_f = (2*n_controls_f) - alt_AC_controls_f;
ref_AC_controls_f = major_AC_controls_f;
major_AF_controls_f = major_AC_controls_f/(2*n_controls_f);
ref_AF_controls_f = major_AF_controls_f;
endif
% female cases + controls-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
alt_AC_complete_samples_f = AC_f;
major_AC_complete_samples_f = alt_AC_complete_samples_f;
alt_AF_complete_samples_f = alt_AC_complete_samples_f/(2*n_complete_samples_f);
major_AF_complete_samples_f = alt_AF_complete_samples_f;
minor_AF_complete_samples_f = minor_AF_f;
ref_AF_complete_samples_f = minor_AF_complete_samples_f;
minor_AC_complete_samples_f = (2*n_complete_samples_f)*minor_AF_complete_samples_f;
ref_AC_complete_samples_f = minor_AC_complete_samples_f;
else
alt_AF_complete_samples_f = minor_AF_f;
minor_AF_complete_samples_f = alt_AF_complete_samples_f;
alt_AC_complete_samples_f = AC_f;
minor_AC_complete_samples_f = alt_AC_complete_samples_f;
ref_AC_complete_samples_f = 2*n_complete_samples_f - alt_AC_complete_samples_f;
major_AC_complete_samples_f = ref_AC_complete_samples_f;
ref_AF_complete_samples_f = ref_AC_complete_samples_f/(2*n_complete_samples_f);
major_AF_complete_samples_f = ref_AF_complete_samples_f;
endif
% male cases-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
alt_AC_cases_m = ytx_m;
major_AC_cases_m = alt_AC_cases_m;
alt_AF_cases_m = alt_AC_cases_m/(2*n_cases_m);
major_AF_cases_m = alt_AF_cases_m;
minor_AC_cases_m = 2*n_cases_m - ytx_m;
ref_AC_cases_m = minor_AC_cases_m;
minor_AF_cases_m = minor_AC_cases_m/(2*n_cases_m);
ref_AF_cases_m = minor_AF_cases_m;
else
alt_AC_cases_m = ytx_m;
minor_AC_cases_m = alt_AC_cases_m;
alt_AF_cases_m = alt_AC_cases_m/(2*n_cases_m);

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minor_AF_cases_m = alt_AF_cases_m;
ref_AC_case_m = 2*n_cases_m - ytx_m;
major_AC_case_m = ref_AC_case_m;
ref_AF_case_m = ref_AC_case_m/(2*n_cases_m);
major_AF_case_m = ref_AF_case_m;
endif
% male controls-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
alt_AC_controls_m = AC_m - alt_AC_cases_m;
major_AC_controls_m = alt_AC_controls_m;
alt_AF_controls_m = alt_AC_controls_m/(2*n_controls_m);
major_AF_controls_m = alt_AF_controls_m;
minor_AC_controls_m = (2*n_controls_m) - alt_AC_controls_m;
ref_AC_controls_m = minor_AC_controls_m;
minor_AF_controls_m = minor_AC_controls_m/(2*n_controls_m);
ref_AF_controls_m = minor_AF_controls_m;
else
alt_AC_controls_m = AC_m - alt_AC_cases_m;
minor_AC_controls_m = alt_AC_controls_m;
alt_AF_controls_m = alt_AC_controls_m/(2*n_controls_m);
minor_AF_controls_m = alt_AF_controls_m;
major_AC_controls_m = (2*n_controls_m) - alt_AC_controls_m;
ref_AC_controls_m = major_AC_controls_m;
major_AF_controls_m = major_AC_controls_m/(2*n_controls_m);
ref_AF_controls_m = major_AF_controls_m;
endif
% male cases + controls-----
if ( AF > 0.5 )
alt_AC_complete_samples_m = AC_m;
major_AC_complete_samples_m = alt_AC_complete_samples_m;
alt_AF_complete_samples_m = alt_AC_complete_samples_m/(2*n_complete_samples_m);
major_AF_complete_samples_m = alt_AF_complete_samples_m;
minor_AF_complete_samples_m = minor_AF_m;
ref_AF_complete_samples_m = minor_AF_complete_samples_m;
minor_AC_complete_samples_m = (2*n_complete_samples_m)*minor_AF_complete_samples_m;
ref_AC_complete_samples_m = minor_AC_complete_samples_m;
else
alt_AF_complete_samples_m = minor_AF_m;
minor_AF_complete_samples_m = alt_AF_complete_samples_m;
alt_AC_complete_samples_m = AC_m;
minor_AC_complete_samples_m = alt_AC_complete_samples_m;
ref_AC_complete_samples_m = 2*n_complete_samples_m - alt_AC_complete_samples_m;
major_AC_complete_samples_m = ref_AC_complete_samples_m;
ref_AF_complete_samples_m = ref_AC_complete_samples_m/(2*n_complete_samples_m);
major_AF_complete_samples_m = ref_AF_complete_samples_m;
endif
% -----
% statistics
% -----
% females-----
p = minor_AF_f;
n = n_cases_f*2;
k = minor_AC_cases_f;
L_C_B=0.;
for i=1:1:k
L_C_B = L_C_B + log10( (n-i+1)/(k-i+1) );
end
log10_p_f = k*log10(p) + (n-k)*log10(1-p) + L_C_B;
p_f = 10^log10_p_f;

```

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% Stirling approximation
p_f_s = (p^k)*((1-p)^(n-k))*(1/sqrt(2*pi*k))*((n/k)^k)*((n/(n-k))^(n-k+0.5));
log10_p_f_s = k*log10(p) + (n-k)*log10(1-p) + log10(1/sqrt(2*pi*k)) + k*log10(n/k) + (n-k+0.5)*log10(n/(n-k));
p_f_s = 10^log10_p_f_s;
% males-----
p = minor_AF_m;
n = n_cases_m*2;
k = minor_AC_cases_m;
L_C_B=0;
for i=1:1:k
    L_C_B = L_C_B + log10( (n-i+1)/(k-i+1) );
end
log10_p_m = k*log10(p) + (n-k)*log10(1-p) + L_C_B;
p_m = 10^log10_p_m;
% Stirling approximation
p_m_s = (p^k)*((1-p)^(n-k))*(1/sqrt(2*pi*k))*((n/k)^k)*((n/(n-k))^(n-k+0.5));
log10_p_m_s = k*log10(p) + (n-k)*log10(1-p) + log10(1/sqrt(2*pi*k)) + k*log10(n/k) + (n-k+0.5)*log10(n/(n-k));
p_m_s = 10^log10_p_m_s;
% -----
% Output
% -----
line = '-----';
disp (line)
disp (alt_string)
disp (minor_string)
disp (line)
% females-----
disp (line)
n_cases_f_string = num2str (n_cases_f);
female_cases_string = strjoin ({'FEMALE CASES. The number of cases is:', n_cases_f_string}, ' ');
disp (female_cases_string)

alt_AC_cases_f_string = num2str (alt_AC_cases_f);
alt_AF_cases_f_string = num2str (alt_AF_cases_f);
alt_female_cases_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,'are:', alt_AC_cases_f_string, \
alt_AF_cases_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_female_cases_string)

ref_AC_cases_f_string = num2str (ref_AC_cases_f);
ref_AF_cases_f_string = num2str (ref_AF_cases_f);
ref_female_cases_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',ref_AC_cases_f_string, \
ref_AF_cases_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (ref_female_cases_string)

disp (line)
n_controls_f_string = num2str (n_controls_f);
female_controls_string = strjoin ({'FEMALE CONTROLS. The number of controls is:', n_controls_f_string}, ' ');
disp (female_controls_string)

alt_AC_controls_f_string = num2str (alt_AC_controls_f);
alt_AF_controls_f_string = num2str (alt_AF_controls_f);
alt_female_controls_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,'are:',alt_AC_controls_f_string,\
alt_AF_controls_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_female_controls_string)

ref_AC_controls_f_string = num2str (ref_AC_controls_f);
ref_AF_controls_f_string = num2str (ref_AF_controls_f);
ref_female_controls_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',ref_AC_controls_f_string,\
ref_AF_controls_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');

```

```

disp (ref_female_controls_string)

disp (line)
p_value = num2str (p_f_s);
st_female_controls_string = strjoin ({'p value is',p_value}, ' ');
disp (st_female_controls_string)

disp (line)
n_complete_samples_f_string = num2str (n_complete_samples_f);
female_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'FEMALE COMPLETE SAMPLE. \
The number of complete samples is:', n_complete_samples_f_string}, ' ');
disp (female_complete_samples_string)

alt_AC_complete_samples_f_string = num2str (alt_AC_complete_samples_f);
alt_AF_complete_samples_f_string = num2str (alt_AF_complete_samples_f);
alt_female_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,\
'are:',alt_AC_complete_samples_f_string,alt_AF_complete_samples_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_female_complete_samples_string)

ref_AC_complete_samples_f_string = num2str (ref_AC_complete_samples_f);
ref_AF_complete_samples_f_string = num2str (ref_AF_complete_samples_f);
ref_female_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',\
ref_AC_complete_samples_f_string,ref_AF_complete_samples_f_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (ref_female_complete_samples_string)
disp (line)

% males-----
disp (line)
n_cases_m_string = num2str (n_cases_m);
male_cases_string = strjoin ({'MALE CASES. The number of cases is:', n_cases_m_string}, ' ');
disp (male_cases_string)

alt_AC_cases_m_string = num2str (alt_AC_cases_m);
alt_AF_cases_m_string = num2str (alt_AF_cases_m);
alt_male_cases_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,'are:', \
alt_AC_cases_m_string, alt_AF_cases_m_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_male_cases_string)

ref_AC_cases_m_string = num2str (ref_AC_cases_m);
ref_AF_cases_m_string = num2str (ref_AF_cases_m);
ref_male_cases_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',ref_AC_cases_m_string, \
ref_AF_cases_m_string, 'respectively' }, ' ');
disp (ref_male_cases_string)

disp (line)
n_controls_m_string = num2str (n_controls_m);
male_controls_string = strjoin ({'MALE CONTROLS. The number of controls is:', n_controls_m_string}, ' ');
disp (male_controls_string)

alt_AC_controls_m_string = num2str (alt_AC_controls_m);
alt_AF_controls_m_string = num2str (alt_AF_controls_m);
alt_male_controls_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,'are:',alt_AC_controls_m_string,\
alt_AF_controls_m_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_male_controls_string)

ref_AC_controls_m_string = num2str (ref_AC_controls_m);
ref_AF_controls_m_string = num2str (ref_AF_controls_m);
ref_male_controls_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',ref_AC_controls_m_string,\
ref_AF_controls_m_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');

```

```

disp (ref_male_controls_string)

disp (line)
p_value = num2str (p_m_s);
st_male_controls_string = strjoin ({'p value is',p_value}, ' ');
disp (st_male_controls_string)

disp (line)
n_complete_samples_m_string = num2str (n_complete_samples_m);
male_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'MALE COMPLETE SAMPLE. The number of complete samples is:',\
n_complete_samples_m_string}, ' ');
disp (male_complete_samples_string)

alt_AC_complete_samples_m_string = num2str (alt_AC_complete_samples_m);
alt_AF_complete_samples_m_string = num2str (alt_AF_complete_samples_m);
alt_male_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',alt_al,'are:',\
alt_AC_complete_samples_m_string,alt_AF_complete_samples_m_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (alt_male_complete_samples_string)

ref_AC_complete_samples_m_string = num2str (ref_AC_complete_samples_m);
ref_AF_complete_samples_m_string = num2str (ref_AF_complete_samples_m);
ref_male_complete_samples_string = strjoin ({'Count and frequency for',ref_al,'are:',\
ref_AC_complete_samples_m_string,ref_AF_complete_samples_m_string, 'respectively'}, ' ');
disp (ref_male_complete_samples_string)
disp (line)

```

2 Genotype and metabolites for a set of five ME/CFS patients

I have access to exomes/genomes of some ME/CFS patients. In Table 9 I have collected the genotype for position Ch13:41353297 (Human H19 reference genome) of 5 ME/CFS patients, reporting metabolic data (blood) for the urea cycle, when available.

Pt.	Sex	rs7337312	ammonium/ ammonia	ornithine	arginine	citrulline	urea
P1	M	GG	↑	=	=	=	=
P2	F	GG	-	-	-	-	-
P3	M	GA	-	↑	=	=	-
P4	F	GG	-	-	-	-	-
P5	F	AA	-	-	-	-	-

Table 9. The genotype of five ME/CFS patients for the position Ch13:41353297 with some metabolic data for urea cycle (blood). Reference genome: Human H19. Symbol '-' indicates that the measure is not available.